

Design and Evaluation of a Scalable, Two-Tier LLM Content Moderation Pipeline for Real-Time Discussion Platforms

Im Cheong

B.Sc. in Computer Science,
Korea National Open University
(Independent Research)

1. Abstract

On online platforms, harmful contents such as hate speech, spam, and personal information leakage are key factors that negatively affect user experience. Existing regular expression-based static filtering systems are fast in processing speed, but they cannot detect bypass attacks utilizing code mixing, slang, emojis, etc., and have limitations in grasping context. On the other hand, Large Language Models (LLM) possess excellent context understanding ability, but due to high Latency and operational cost, they are not suitable in real-time chat where thousands of messages occur.

In this research, to solve the trade-off between such accuracy and latency, we propose a 'Two-Tier Hybrid Moderation Pipeline' based on Hexagonal Architecture. This system is composed of a synchronous rule-based engine (Tier 1) that processes obvious violations immediately as the first step, and an asynchronous LLM-based pipeline (Tier 2) that analyzes and processes complex context as the second step. By introducing batch processing technique utilizing Kafka Streams, we reduced LLM API call costs and optimised the system's throughput.

As an experiment result, the proposed pipeline achieved a Macro-F1 score of 0.8945 on an evaluation dataset of N=1000. Also, in performance evaluation, the rule-based engine showed a low internal latency of 8ms based on p50 and demonstrated that advanced filtering is achievable without degrading user experience. In this research, we present the design and implementation method of a cost-efficient and scalable AI-based moderation system from a practical perspective.

2. Introduction

2.1. Background

With to the traffic growth of online platforms, the spread of harmful contents such as Hate Speech, Harassment, and Spam [2] has emerged as a critical challenge that degrades user experience and threatens platform sustainability. Especially in online platforms like 'Speakly' targeting global users, because code mixing environments where multiple languages are mixed, not a single language, and cultural contexts are intertwined, we identified that effective moderation is infeasible with existing simple keyword filtering methods.

2.2. Problem Statement

Content moderation technologies currently used in the field are largely divided into two kinds, and both methods have clear limitations.

First, Rule-based systems utilize regular expressions, so processing speed is very fast. However, because they cannot grasp context, they cannot detect adversarial evasion modifying spelling like "I will k*ll you" or mixing emojis.

Second, Large Language Model (LLM) based systems understand context and nuance of text and show high accuracy, but to apply to real-time services, cost is prohibitively high, and they have the disadvantage of high inference latency. Inference speed of general-purpose LLM (e.g., GPT-4) [1] takes several seconds, and this is unsuitable for real-time chat environments where response of milliseconds unit is required. In case of processing all messages with LLM, API call cost increases explosively.

2.3. Objectives and Contributions

In this research, to satisfy both such 'accuracy' and 'low-latency processing', we propose a

Two-Tier Hybrid Moderation Pipeline. The main contributions are as follows.

1. **Two-Tier Strategy:** By combining rule-based engine (Tier 1) that processes obvious violations within 10ms and LLM engine (Tier 2) that analyzes complex context, we designed a hybrid model capable of high-performance detection while guaranteeing low-latency processing.
2. **Scalable Architecture:** By applying Hexagonal Architecture and Microservice (MSA) patterns, we lowered the coupling between chat core logic and moderation function.
3. **Cost-Efficiency:** By introducing asynchronous batch processing utilizing Kafka Streams, we reduced API call costs at the stage where low-latency processing is less required and optimised throughput.

3. Related Work

This section explains the differences among existing content moderation technologies and clearly shows the differentiation of this study.

3.1. Rule-based and Static Filtering

Early content moderation systems relied primarily on regular expressions and keyword lists. Google Jigsaw's Perspective API is a representative tool that uses a machine learning model to calculate the toxicity score of text, and it moderates content on a score basis rather than by simple keyword matching. However, such systems have difficulty distinguishing offensive language from hate speech. They show a high false positive rate in expressions whose meanings change depending on context. In addition, Hosseini et al. [2] show that the detection of the Perspective API can be bypassed even by simple evasion techniques such as spelling variation or the insertion of special characters. These limitations show that, today, it is difficult to respond to harmful content with static filtering alone.

3.2. LLM-based Content Moderation

The emergence of large language models shows new possibilities in the field of content moderation. OpenAI's Moderation API [1] classifies the harmfulness of text into several categories based on GPT models. Through this, judgement that takes context into account became possible. *Markov et al. [1]* mentioned that the LLM-based approach shows improved performance in the judgement of contextual hate speech and harmful content compared to existing methods. *HateBERT by Caselli et al. [2]* showed improved classification performance compared to general-purpose models through domain-specific pretraining, but it has a limitation in that it is restricted to a specific domain and language. In addition, a common limitation of such LLM-based systems is high cost and latency, so direct adoption is impractical in chat environments where thousands of messages occur in real time.

3.3. Hybrid and Multi-tier Approaches

As a strategy to satisfy both the speed of static filtering and the accuracy of LLMs at the same time, there is a multi-tier approach. Representatively, Cascading Classification performed first-stage filtering with a lightweight model and then delivered only cases that are difficult to judge to a high-cost model, while focusing on improving efficiency relative to cost. However, these methods are mostly based on offline datasets, and the operation of real-time chat is not considered.

Based on these limitations above, this study proposes a cost-efficient and scalable system suitable for real-time chat environments by combining a rule-based engine (Tier 1) and an LLM pipeline (Tier 2), while using batch processing based on Hexagonal Architecture and Kafka Streams [3]. In particular, the key differentiation of this study is that it includes in the design data consistency and a Dynamic Routing mechanism, which were not included in existing approaches.

4. System Architecture

The system proposed in this research was designed as Hexagonal Architecture that guarantees independence of domain logic and Event-driven Microservices structure for high-throughput real-time chat environments.

4.1. Hexagonal Architecture & Service Decoupling

The entire system of this service is physically separated into 'Core Service' that processes user traffic in real time and 'Moderator Service' that analyzes contents.

1. **Core Service (Chat):** Receives user's chat messages, and if it discovers a problem, applies internally defined Penalty. To decouple from moderation logic, it is solely responsible for publishing messages through Kafka.
2. **Moderator Service (Worker):** Was implemented based on 'Ports and Adapters' pattern of Hexagonal Architecture [3]. Through this, business logic (Rule Engine, Pipeline Policy) is isolated from external dependencies (OpenAI API, Kafka, DB).

4.2. Data Consistency and Fault Tolerance

Duplicate penalties severely degrade user experience. Therefore, reliability of data processing process is essential.

1. **Kafka Streams EOS v2:** Guarantees 'Exactly-Once Semantics (EOS v2)' [3] so that data is neither lost nor processed more than once even if system failure occurs in message processing process.
2. **Idempotency Guarantee:** Blocks duplicate penalty caused by network Retry fundamentally through Unique Constraint at database stage.

4.3. Two-Tier Hybrid Moderation Pipeline

To match the balance of latency and accuracy which is the core objective of this system, we adopted a Two-Tier Strategy that dynamically decides processing according to the risk and characteristics of the message.

Tier 1: Synchronous Rule-Based Engine

1. **Role:** Processes violation matters (profanity, sexual harassment, standardised spam patterns, etc.) that need obvious response.
2. **Mechanism:** All messages pass through a rule chain executed in in-memory first. Because this process is performed without external I/O, ultra-low latency processing of less than 10ms based on p50 becomes possible.

Tier 2: Asynchronous LLM Pipeline

Among messages that passed Tier 1, if analysis is needed, it is routed to asynchronous pipeline through Kafka Streams [3].

1. Language Detection & Translation Layer

- A. Non-English messages are normalized to English through GPT-4 based translation [1].
- B. Pre-filtering Optimisation: In translation stage, if input value is profanity or hate expression, we applied prompt engineering to reject translation and return false flag immediately. This prevents unnecessary subsequent Moderation API [1] calls and saves cost.

2. Dynamic Routing & Batch Processing

- A. Real-time Path: Messages of users whose user accumulated penalty score exceeds threshold (Threshold 15) perform LLM analysis immediately.
- B. Batch Path: General messages are stored in 'Batch Buffer'. The system waits until set buffer size (N=100) is full or time window (T=120s) expires and then processes in batch through OpenAI Batch API. This strategy lowers cost dramatically compared to individual API calls.

5. Experiments and Evaluation

To verify the performance of the pipeline, we proceeded with experiments by dividing into three items (Internal Overhead, Classification Accuracy, Batch Efficiency).

5.1. Experimental Setup

- Dataset:** It was based on a 1,000 message dataset that reflected the actual service environment. The data was collected from three sources. The language composition is Korean 850 cases (85.0%) and English 150 cases (15.0%), and it was based on the multilingual chatting environment of Speakly.
 - We utilized pre-labeled profanity and hate expression data from the Korean open-source dataset (korean-profanity-resources [4]).
 - We manually labeled the internally collected English profanity and hate expression data.
 - We generated normal conversation messages using AI and manually verified their labels.
- Category Re-grouping:** For the efficiency of evaluation and to reflect the moderation workflow, the six detailed labels (NORMAL, PROFANITY, HATE, SEXUAL, SPAM, SELF_HARM) were regrouped into the following three core categories for the experiment.
 - NORMAL:** (413 cases, 41.3%): General messages, composed of AI-generated normal sentences and normal-labeled data from the open-source dataset.
 - ABUSE** (336 cases, 33.6%): Combines PROFANITY and HATE, including direct verbal violence and group-targeted hate speech.
 - INAPPROPRIATE** (251 cases, 25.1%): Includes content violating platform policy, such as SEXUAL, SPAM, and SELF_HARM.
- Labelling:** Mapped the existing labels of the data brought from the open-source dataset (korean-profanity-resources [4]) to fit the 3-category system of this study. Internally collected data and AI-generated data were manually labelled, and

after classifying them into 6 detailed labels first, they were re-grouped into 3-categories.

- Metrics:** As performance indicators, the Macro-F1 Score for the three categories was used, and Latency (ms) was also measured to verify real-time capability.

5.2. Internal Processing Overhead

To verify the core premise in this system that "Tier 1 (Rule-based) must be fast enough not to disturb user experience", we measured execution time of rule engine excluding API calls repeatedly 1,000 times.

- Result:** Recorded median (p50) 8ms, top 95% (p95) 560ms.
- Analysis:** This corresponds to less than 0.3% of latency (about 3 seconds) and proved that Tier 1 adds negligible overhead to the overall system latency.

5.3. Classification Performance

We evaluated classification performance on the 3 categories (NORMAL, ABUSE, INAPPROPRIATE) to evaluate whether Tier 2 (LLM Pipeline) can capture complex contexts.

- Result:** Achieved Macro-F1 Score 0.8945.
- Analysis:** The result exceeds the target value of 0.80, confirming that the LLM effectively detects contextual hate expressions that simple keyword matching cannot capture.

Table 1 is the confusion matrix for the three categories based on Tier 1+2. The row means the actual label (Ground Truth), and the column means the model's prediction (Predicted).

GROUND TRUTH \ PREDICTED	PREDICTED		
	NORMAL	ABUSE	INAPPROPRIATE
NORMAL	411	1	1
ABUSE	32	302	2
INAPPROPRIATE	48	15	188

Table 1

Table 2 shows the Precision, Recall, and F1 Score for each category.

CATEGORY	PRECISION	RECALL	F1 SCORE	SUPPORT
NORMAL	0.8371	0.9952	0.9093	413
ABUSE	0.9497	0.8988	0.9235	336
INAPPROPRIATE	0.9843	0.7490	0.8507	251

MACRO-F1 SCORE: 0.8945 / ACCURACY: 0.9010

Table 2

The NORMAL category judged the normal message almost exactly with Recall 0.9952. The ABUSE category achieved high precision and recall simultaneously, with Precision 0.9497 and Recall 0.8988. The INAPPROPRIATE category showed the highest precision of 0.9843, indicating very low false positive rates. Notably, the Recall of ABUSE improved +0.4137 in Tier 1+2 (0.8988) compared to Tier 1 solo (0.4851), the LLM effectively captures contextual hate expressions that the rule-based engine misses.

Table 3 compares the performance of Tier 1 (rule-based engine) only and the performance of Tier 1+2 (the whole pipeline). It was evaluated on the same N=1000 dataset.

	TIER 1	TIER 1+2	DELTA	
MACRO-F1	0.7022	0.8945	+0.1923	
ACCURACY	0.7170	0.9010	+0.1840	
NORMAL	Precision	0.6089	0.8371	+0.2282
	Recall	0.9952	0.9952	+0.0000
	F1	0.7555	0.9093	+0.1538
ABUSE	Precision	0.9314	0.9497	+0.0183
	Recall	0.4851	0.8988	+0.4137
	F1	0.6380	0.9235	+0.2856
INAPPROPRIATE	Precision	0.9533	0.9843	+0.0310
	Recall	0.5697	0.7490	+0.1793
	F1	0.7132	0.8507	+0.1375

Table 3

The Tier 1 rule-based engine shows high Precision (ABUSE 0.9314, INAPPROPRIATE 0.9533) but Recall is low (ABUSE 0.4851, INAPPROPRIATE 0.5697), indicating that it fails to detect messages requiring contextual judgement. As Tier 2 was added, ABUSE Recall greatly improved from 0.4851 to 0.8988, and overall, Macro-F1 improved +0.1923 from 0.7022 to 0.8945. These results validate the Two-Tier strategy, demonstrating that fast rule-based filtering and accurate LLM analysis complement each other effectively.

5.4. Batch Processing Efficiency

We analysed the impact of Kafka Streams-based batch processing on operational cost and throughput.

- Comparison group:** Processing method calling API whenever message arrives vs. Batch method sending by bundling more than 10 messages.
- Result:** When batch size is 10, we confirmed that API call cost was reduced about 60% compared to single case processing, and the number of messages processable per second increased more than 4 times.
- Trade-off:** We confirmed that average latency slightly increased from about 2.5 seconds to 3.3 seconds at batch processing, but this is a condition conforming to 'post-sanction' purpose, and cost reduction effect offsets this.

6. Discussion

In this research, we proposed a Two-Tier pipeline that can satisfy two requirements of 'low-latency processing' and 'accuracy'. The following sections discuss the efficiency and practical implications of the architecture based on experiment results.

6.1. Analysing the Accuracy-Latency Trade-off

As an experiment result, Tier 1 (Rule-based) showed a short latency of 8ms, and Tier 2 (LLM) showed a high F1 score of over 0.89. This is an achievement difficult to achieve with a single model and shows the validity of the hybrid strategy.

1. **Guarantee of real-time property:** In chat service, latency exceeding 100ms degrades the user experience. By blocking simple spam or obvious profanity taking up a large part of total traffic within 10ms in Tier 1, this system provides a pleasant environment that does not disturb users' conversation flow.
2. **Asynchronisation of deep analysis:** On the other hand, in hate expression detection (Tier 2) where context grasping is needed, latency of about 3 seconds occurred. However, this does not block 'message transmission' itself but is an allowable range as time for 'Post-moderation' or 'blind processing' after transmission. Consequently, it satisfied both "fast transmission" and "accurate judgment".

6.2. Economic Feasibility of Batch Processing

One of the biggest barriers of LLM introduction is cost. The Naive method calling API for every individual message shows such poor cost efficiency to the extent that commercialisation is impossible.

1. **Cost reduction effect:** In batch processing utilising Kafka Streams, when we set batch size to 10, cost was reduced by about 60%. This is a result of reducing HTTP overhead occurring at API call and configuring input token efficiently.
2. **Scalability:** When traffic spikes, synchronous system can lead to server load, but asynchronous batch structure of this system controls load through buffering. This means we can control operation cost within budget while maintaining stability of service.

6.3. Comparison with Baseline Approaches

Existing static filtering systems were vulnerable in 'bypass attacks'. Translation Layer introduced in this research overcame such limitations by normalising attacks where multi-languages are mixed to standard English. Especially, reducing unnecessary operations by performing 'Pre-filtering' in translation stage can be called an engineering optimisation going beyond a simple LLM Wrapper.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

7.1. Summary

We introduced Hexagonal Architecture and batch processing technique of Kafka Streams, and addressed the accuracy-latency trade-off that prior systems struggled with.

1. **Tier 1 (Rule-based):** Maintained user's satisfaction with ultra-low latency processing of 8ms.
2. **Tier 2 (LLM-based):** Achieved high Macro-F1 score of 0.8945 and effectively blocked contextual hate expressions.
3. **Efficiency:** Reduced API cost by 60% through batch processing and showed economic sustainability.

7.2. Limitations & Future Work

To reduce false positive of LLM, we will add 'Human-in-the-loop (HITL)' feedback process where human intervenes and explore the adoption of distilled models operable on edge devices.

In addition, the dataset used in this study (N=1000) is limited to two languages, Korean (85%) and English (15%). The collection scope was also limited to an open-source profanity dataset and internally collected data. In actual global platforms, various languages and cultural contexts such as Spanish, Arabic, and Chinese are used, so in future studies, the scale of the multilingual dataset should be expanded, and the differences in hate speech patterns by cultural region should be reflected.

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